

Transpersonal Psychotherapy

Princy Abraham

Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatric Nursing, School of Nursing, Galgotias University, Greater Noida U.P

ABSTRACT

Concept of Transpersonal Psychotherapy is mainly focused on the spiritual aspects of human life which will be integrated with counselling and a better understanding of self and help in setting the life goals. This therapy was firstly termed in 1960s by the psychologists to examine and apply the theories of spirituality in the healing process of mind and soul. The psychologist has included the spiritual aspect to help the clients to attain the optimum level of self-accomplishment

Keywords: Psychotherapy, Spirituality healing, Mind relationship.

INTRODUCTION

“Everything that irritates us about others can lead us to a better understanding of ourselves” (Jung)

Psychotherapy is a process involving the therapist and the client towards a goal of developing positive thinking and coping skills to treat the emotional issues and mental traumas.

There are many therapies in the field of psychiatry which help the individual to alleviate his suffering and enhance the wellbeing, and one among them is the Transpersonal Psychotherapy which is newly introduced and practiced in many countries successfully.

Aims

Transpersonal Therapy that aims at alleviating the mental tensions and helping the individual in attention and concertation. It is a comprehensive approach allowing the person to identify the issues related to the mental, physical, social, emotional and creative aspects of life and it also pays importance in spiritual healing.

Origin

The concept of transpersonal therapy was initiated after the works of Carl Jung, William James, and Abraham Maslow, with their main goal in discovering body and mind relationship and their inner connections with emphasised role of spirituality in modifying the human behaviour.

Description

Transpersonal therapy is an innovative approach of traditional method of healing with the modern aspects of psychology and discovering the new dimensions and solving issues of human behaviour.

Transpersonal therapist helps the client to explore the wide range of issues within the clients which include personal and physical and spiritual. It will help the client to self-identify the issues through the introspection of his wide experiences. Therefore, it provides a holistic approach towards the individual expressions and experiences which will also explore the needs and desires of the individual and the self and others expectations.

This therapy is mainly used for the people who become deviated and confused while searching for inner peace and spirituality and also who experience anxiety, phobias, depression, addiction and depression where one need to explore and search the peace and resolution within self.

The therapist primarily and vitally implements various methods which bring calmness and deviations from the provoking areas, which may include yoga, meditation, hypnotherapy, guided imagery, various arts which help the client to explore self , create spirituality and through which they are helped to find meaning of their life and the purpose of their existence.

In Transpersonal therapy the spiritual leaders can be involved based on the belief of the individual, at the same time this therapy is not restricted to any religion and neither promoting or prophesising any religion.

The clients are encouraged to express their spiritual views and realize the actual understanding of life. Transpersonal therapy proves itself differ from the other therapies because it is not always looking for a diseased one but understand that this therapy can be naturally applied to all individual who need to understand the self-worth and all the linkages between the self, environment and the spirit. This help to give a crystal meaning to life and new dimensions of it.

There is no specialized educational qualification for the Transpersonal Therapist. Any person who has acquired degree or doctorate in psychology or in

counselling can proceed for the transpersonal counselling.

Transpersonal therapy is still in the budding stage and may need few years to become a full-fledged and recommended therapy in all over the world.

CONCLUSION

Transpersonal psychotherapy helps the individual to grow and acquire the satisfaction in each stage of growth and development. It also helps the individual to obtain higher level of consciousness. This therapy not only focuses on the human body and mind but also emphasizes on the spiritual growth and development of an individual. The therapist may use many concepts and practices from various religions that can help to explore and identify various behavioural and mindful modifications. It will guide the individual to be comfortably adaptive in the dynamic society and also in the bothered times of the life.

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